

HadISDH.land Update Document

Kate Willett (MOHC), 8th March 2022

General Notes:

The HadISDH.land.v4.4.0.2021f contains all 12 months of 2021. It is a minor new version (Y element + 1) because the climatological reference period has changed from 1981-2010 to 1919-2020, in line with WMO recommendations. All other processing steps for HadISDH.land remain identical. The new version of HadISD (3.2.0.2021f) has pulled through some historical changes to stations which are passed on to HadISDH.land but the initial station base of 9279 stayed the same. The change in climatology period has led to more stations meeting the record completeness criteria, increasing the HadISDH processing station base from 4520 to 5581. The end station count is further reduced after homogenisation. The homogeneity adjustments differ slightly due to sensitivity to the addition and loss of stations, historical changes to stations previously included and the additional 12 months of data. More information can be found at <https://hadisdh.blogspot.com/2022/03/2021-update-from-hadisdhlandv4402021f.html>.

Version Number X.Y.Z.0000p/f:

4.4.0.2021f

Major Changes X:

- None

Minor Changes Y:

- The climatological reference period has changed from 1981-2010 to 1991-2020. Station completeness criteria are based on data presence over the climatology period so this has affected station selection.

Bug fixes / historical data updates Z:

- Retrospective improvements to the historical data in the ISD archive are ongoing and have been incorporated here. As the Y element has already been increased no increment is applied to the Z element.

Start Date DD.MM.YYYY: 1973-01-01

End Date DD.MM.YYYY: 2021-12-31

Hadisdh Data Format (Baseline documentation): URL: <http://cedadocs.ceda.ac.uk/1477>

Reference: No change

Other notes: The update blog post is here: <https://hadisdh.blogspot.com/2022/03/2021-update-from-hadisdhlandv4402021f.html>